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El papel de la cultura del lugar de trabajo en la integración social del empleado: Estudio de un caso práctico

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Resumen. La cultura corporativa ha sido objeto de atención durante muchos años y se reconoce cada vez más como un factor clave que da forma a la identidad única de las organizaciones. Permite a las empresas destacar, atraer a empleados con talento y fidelizar a sus clientes. Este estudio pretende elaborar recomendaciones para mejorar la cultura corporativa de las grandes empresas identificando la relación entre la cultura corporativa y los valores individuales de los empleados. El estudio de caso está representado por el mayor banco privado de Rusia, Alfa-Bank. Los métodos de investigación primaria incluyeron encuestas a empleados y entrevistas en profundidad, acompañadas de un análisis cuantitativo y cualitativo de los resultados. Las recomendaciones incluyen mejorar el proceso de incorporación, abordar la cuestión de las horas extraordinarias, implantar sistemas en línea para presentar solicitudes de dotación de personal y pago de horas extraordinarias, y organizar reuniones, sesiones de intercambio de ideas y programas de formación para fomentar el potencial creativo de los empleados. Los resultados serán valiosos para ejecutivos y profesionales de RRHH de grandes empresas, así como para consultores empresariales e investigadores académicos interesados en mejorar la cultura corporativa y explorar la relación entre los valores corporativos e individuales dentro de las organizaciones.

Palabras clave: cultura empresarial, valores individuales, capital humano, mejora de la cultura empresarial.

The role of workplace culture in social integration of employee: Case study

Abstract. Corporate culture has been a subject of attention for many years and is increasingly recognized as a key factor shaping the unique identity of organizations. It enables companies to stand out, attract talented employees, and build a loyal customer base. This study aims to develop recommendations for improving the corporate culture of large corporations by identifying the relationship between corporate culture and individual employee values. The case study is represented by Russia's largest private bank, Alfa-Bank. The primary research methods included employee surveys and in-depth interviews, accompanied by quantitative and qualitative analysis of the results. The recommendations include improving the onboarding process, addressing the issue of overtime, implementing online systems for submitting staffing and overtime payment requests, and organizing meetups, brainstorming sessions, and training programs to foster the creative potential of employees. The results will be valuable to executives and HR professionals in large corporations, as well as business consultants and academic researchers interested in enhancing corporate culture and exploring the relationship between corporate and individual values within organizations.

Key words: corporate culture, individual values, human capital, improvement of corporate culture.

INTRODUCTION

The academic community has not formed a unified approach to the relationship between corporate culture and employee values (Kurgansky et al., 2022; Zueva et al., 2022). Research in this area is typically conducted either from the company's perspective or with a focus on employee loyalty and satisfaction. While various methods exist for assessing employee values-based orientations, their interrelation often depends on the specific framework adopted by different scholars (Kochetkova, 2024).

This study aims to develop recommendations for improving the corporate culture of large corporations by identifying the relationship between corporate culture and individual employee values. The research object is Russia's largest private bank, Alfa-Bank. The research subject is the relationship between Alfa-Bank's corporate culture and the individual values of its employees.

The study set out the following tasks:

- 1) To explore the theoretical foundations of the concepts of corporate culture and individual employee values;
- 2) To analyze the corporate culture and the individual values of employees and managers within a large corporation;
- 3) To assess the degree of alignment between the corporate culture and the individual values of the corporation's employees;
- 4) To develop recommendations for shaping a corporate culture responsive to internal and external changes and consider the influence of individual employee values.

The study addresses a range of issues, including various approaches to defining corporate culture, the characteristics of different cultural types, and the methods for forming, maintaining, and improving corporate culture. Furthermore, it highlights the importance of examining employees' values and their potential impact on organizational performance.

The results may prove valuable for executives and human resource professionals in large corporations seeking to enhance their corporate culture and increase employee satisfaction. In addition, the proposed recommendations are relevant for business consultants and academic researchers focused on the interaction between corporate and individual values within organizations.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Corporate culture is an integral part of any modern organization. M. Armstrong describes corporate culture as a set of shared beliefs, values, behavioral norms, and attitudes held by all employees within an organization (Armstrong, 1998). According to S. Robbins and P. Stephen, corporate culture plays a crucial role in shaping a company's image and highlighting its unique characteristics (Robbins, 1994). G. Hofstede and M. Minkov in their book "Cultures and Organizations: Software of the Mind" (2005) identified six key dimensions for evaluating the corporate cultures of countries and organizations: power distance (1), uncertainty avoidance (2), individualism/collectivism (3), masculinity/femininity (4), long-term orientation (5), indulgence/restraint (6). In Russian organizations, the main cultural dimensions tend to be high power distance, individualism, and uncertainty avoidance (Tsoi & Kochetkova, 2023). F. Trompenaars' classification of corporate culture is also one of the most well-known and widely accepted tools for analyzing and understanding various aspects of organizational culture (Table 1).

TABLE 1. Trompenaars' classification of corporate culture

Comparable parameters	Egalitarianism (equality)	Hierarchy
Person	Incubator – Achievement-oriented culture	Family-Power-oriented culture
Goal	Guided missile – Task-oriented culture	Eiffel Tower-Role-oriented culture

Source: Compiled by the authors based on (Persikova, 2020).

Cameron & Quinn identify the following types of corporate culture: clan (family) culture, adhocracy culture, market (entrepreneurial) culture, and hierarchical (bureaucratic) culture (Ulbasheva & Shakova, 2016). Using Cameron and Quinn's Competing Values Culture Model, it is possible to determine an organization's cultural type and categorize it into one of these four groups. This enables the analysis of organizational issues and provides insights into why certain goals may not be achieved (The World of Work Project, n.d.).

Overall, the value of organizational culture lies in its ability to enhance internal cohesion and foster consistency in employee behavior (Togaibayeva et al., 2023). From the employee's perspective, organizational culture serves as a kind of compass, guiding them toward the appropriate behaviors required for success within the organization (Laukart-Gorbacheva et al., 2021).

Values serve as guiding principles that people strive toward and hold in high regard. Although values are largely intangible and spiritual, they are ultimately expressed through specific

actions (Khasyanova, 2013). Individual employee values are a set of personal traits and characteristics that shape their capacity for such types of activity. Understanding these individual values allows an organization to influence the development of its corporate culture (Hofstede & Minkov, 2005). In recent years, the H2H (human-to-human) theory has gained popularity. This theory emphasizes that the relationship between managers who serve as key representatives of an organization's values and employees should be built on openness, friendliness, and emotional intelligence (Yusupova, 2022).

Let us consider Milton Rokeach's approach to the classification of values-based orientations, which is based on direct ranking (Rokich, 1973):

- 1) Terminal values represent the understanding that any ultimate personal goal is worth striving for;
- 2) Instrumental values reflect the belief that a certain set of means or modes of behavior is essential in any given situation.

Individual values benefit organizations as they help identify employees' priorities and goals and contribute to developing a corporate culture that considers these values.

METHODS

The research methods used in this study included a review of scientific literature and internal documents of Alfa-Bank, as well as employee surveys and in-depth interviews. Alfa-Bank's corporate culture was analyzed using a survey that included questions aimed at assessing employee loyalty, satisfaction, engagement, and conflict levels. Employee loyalty was measured based on the likelihood of recommending the company to a potential employee. The survey explored the reasons why employees would recommend the company. 104 employees from various departments participated, with the respondent pool comprising 40% managers and 60% specialists and interns.

The analysis of individual employee values at Alfa-Bank was based on M. Rokeach's methodology. Employees were asked to rank the importance of terminal and instrumental values in their lives. To accommodate the survey format, the list was shortened to nine values of each type. In addition, the type of organizational culture at Alfa-Bank was determined using the culture typology developed by Cameron & Quinn.

The information base for this research includes Alfa-Bank's official reports, original data collected through surveys and interviews, academic articles, and books dedicated to corporate culture and individual employee values.

RESULTS

Alfa-Bank is the largest private bank in Russia. It operates over 300 Phygital offices — next-generation bank branches that combine digital and physical formats of customer interaction (Alfa-Bank, 2023). The mission and vision of Alfa-Bank are articulated as follows: "We help people and businesses improve their lives by providing simple and convenient solutions, from everyday tasks to the most important matters. Today and for years to come" (Alfa-Bank, n.d.). The bank's mission and values are closely aligned with the worldview of its shareholders and employees.

Within the framework of this study, Alfa-Bank's corporate culture was analyzed through employee surveys. The survey examined the reasons why employees would recommend the company. The most commonly cited factors were the team and the tasks. This indicates a positive work environment within the bank, which was also frequently mentioned as a reason for recommending Alfa-Bank as a place to work (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Reasons for recommending Alfa-Bank as an employer

Source: compiled by the authors.

Among the reasons that may hinder employee recommendations are poor onboarding, overtime work, task-related challenges, and workplace atmosphere. These negative job characteristics were identified by only some survey participants (25%). This indicates that some employees are fully satisfied with the work process (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Reasons for not recommending Alfa-Bank as an employer

Source: compiled by the authors.

The job satisfaction score among managers was 3.36, while specialists rated their satisfaction at 2.98. For specialists, the most significant factors contributing to satisfaction were competent leadership, workplace relationships, and pride in their work. The engagement level among managers was assessed at 4.53, compared to 4.04 for specialists. Managers demonstrated the highest willingness to support their colleagues.

Individual employee values in Alfa-Bank were analyzed using Rokeach’s methodology. Participants were asked to rate the importance of achieving terminal and instrumental values in their lives. To facilitate the survey, the list was reduced to nine values of each type. The results indicate that the most important values for managers are creativity, personal growth, social recognition, and financial security (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Terminal values of Alfa-Bank employees

Source: Compiled by the authors

For managerial staff, more specific values aimed at professional self-fulfillment are typical. In contrast, specialists tend to prioritize values such as freedom, public recognition, creativity, and engaging work. This category of employees is more inclined toward abstract values oriented towards personal life.

Instrumental values, which define preferred behavior models, were also analyzed as part of the study (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Instrumental values of Alfa-Bank employees

Source: Compiled by the authors

The most important values for managers were education, cheerfulness, diligence, and responsibility. This indicates a strong emphasis on communication and ethical behavior. For specialists, the highest values were honesty, diligence, independence, and tolerance. In this case, employees value not only interpersonal communication but also self-assertion.

While the values of managers and specialists are largely similar, there are certain differences. For example, in terms of terminal values, managers tend to prioritize personal development, whereas specialists place greater importance on freedom and engaging work. While development and interesting work can positively influence organizational performance, the value of freedom prioritized by specialists may lead to conflict.

Interviews with corporate employees revealed the influence of formal leaders on corporate culture within departments. The respondents generally agreed that managers create a team atmosphere focused on achieving results. They also claimed that leaders show loyalty toward employees who are forced to take time off and emphasize clarity, precision, and a fact-based approach when reviewing their performance.

The analysis of the conflict environment revealed a low degree of value-related contradictions among the personnel. Employees state that conflicts within the organization are rare, and effective conflict resolution mechanisms are in place. Conflict resolution is typically achieved either through independent discussions among the parties involved or with the assistance of a supervisor. In most cases, those involved in conflicts strive to reach a compromise rather than prove themselves right.

According to the classification of organizational cultures developed by Cameron & Quinn, the type of corporate culture at Alfa-Bank was identified. The results of the assessment indicate relatively balanced scores across all culture types (clan – 2.5, adhocracy – 2.67, market – 2.5, hierarchy – 2.33). Despite formal processes within the organization, the dominant culture type was identified as adhocratic. This suggests that Alfa-Bank is a flexible organization focused on external market positioning and achieving results.

Thus, it can be concluded that there is a partial synergy between the values of Alfa-Bank and those of its employees. This is reflected in the shared commitment to meeting customer needs, caring for employees, and incorporating creative approaches into work processes. The desire for independence in decision-making is more common among junior specialists with less professional experience. Such values may foster the discovery of new ways of conducting business and promote individual responsibility for one's contributions to the team and management.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the research conducted, specific recommendations were developed for establishing and enhancing the corporate culture of large companies. These recommendations cover seven key areas.

The first area concerns the development of a strategy for forming corporate culture. It is essential to implement updated corporate values in a top-down manner, starting with the CEO and senior management, while also considering individual employee values. This approach can help increase staff loyalty, job satisfaction, and engagement.

The second important aspect addresses the issue of overtime. It is necessary to create an online reporting system that allows employees to request staff expansion or compensation for overtime work. In addition, guidelines should be developed for submitting staffing requests, and a user-friendly system for filing overtime payment applications should be introduced through corporate digital platforms.

The third area refers to the improvement of the onboarding process. It is recommended to organize introductory meetings between new employees and team leaders, establish a centralized information base on colleagues within the department and adjacent units, and train mentors with clearly defined roles in guiding interns. A key element is the arrangement of regular meetings between mentors and newcomers to review progress and plan further development.

The fourth area involves organizing internal events to support the implementation of changes. An effective solution would be to hold conferences with the participation of psychologists and HR specialists to present new procedures related to overtime and staffing changes. Meetings with mentors/leaders are also useful for aligning tasks regarding new employee adaptation. Broad communication with staff can be achieved through email newsletters and posts in corporate blogs.

The development of corporate culture through informal activities represents the fifth area. It is advisable to organize meetups that encourage knowledge sharing, hold regular brainstorming sessions for idea generation and innovation, and implement business training programs that foster employees' creative thinking.

The sixth area is related to student upskilling programs. It is proposed to develop joint educational initiatives (for example, in collaboration with the Financial University under the Government of the Russian Federation in project management), as well as to organize courses, after which the most successful students would be offered internships at Alfa-Bank.

Finally, the seventh area focuses on strengthening corporate culture through a values-based system. Special attention should be given to values such as caring for others, tolerance, and the pursuit of creativity and personal growth. Supporting these values through targeted events and programs contributes to employees' professional development but also their deeper engagement in the corporate environment.

The comprehensive implementation of these recommendations will contribute not only to the development of a resilient corporate culture but also to increased employee satisfaction and enhanced economic efficiency for the company.

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